

Transforming Assets: The Role of Language in Enhancing Value and Communication.

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Annotation: Asset Transformation the exchange by a company of one type of asset for another. For example, advances in information and communication technologies that allow organizations to quickly and reliably collect information about customer demand have allowed inventories to be reduced. In this way, assets in the form of finished products have been transformed into assets in the form of information. Based on the concept that language in human communication is the main tool and the main communication mechanism to achieve what is real, it is evident that today it is a phenomenon that applies to all forms of business[3:22]. This research aims to identify the role of language strategy in international business relations in order to better understand the importance of knowing the most prominent and influential languages in the trade of goods and services in all business segments[1:19]. Although the importance of English language skills and their role in international business relations is recognized, much more needs to be done to further research this issue. Of course, there are studies on the relationship between language and international business, but few studies have been conducted on the impact of language on international business relations.

Key words: Value Enhancement, Communication Strategies, Linguistic Impact, Stakeholder Engagement, Brand Messaging, Narrative Building, Value Proposition, Persuasive Language, Market Perception, Business Communication.

Annotatsiya: Aktivlarni o'zgartirish - kompaniya tomonidan bir turdagi aktivlarni boshqasiga almashtirish. Masalan, tashkilotlarga mijozlar talabi haqidagi ma'lumotlarni tez va ishonchli to'plash imkonini beruvchi axborot-kommunikatsiya texnologiyalarining rivojlanishi tovar-moddiy zaxiralarni qisqartirish imkonini berdi. Shunday qilib, tayyor mahsulot ko'rinishidagi aktivlar axborot ko'rinishidagi aktivlarga aylantirildi. Insonlar muloqotida til real narsaga erishishning asosiy vositasi va asosiy aloqa mexanizmi ekanligi haqidagi tushunchaga asoslanib, bugungi kunda u biznesning barcha shakllariga taalluqli hodisa ekanligi ayon bo'ladi. Ushbu tadqiqot biznesning barcha segmentlarida tovarlar va xizmatlar savdosida eng mashhur va nufuzli tillarni bilish muhimligini yaxshiroq tushunish uchun xalqaro biznes munosabatlarida til strategiyasining rolini aniqlashga qaratilgan. Ingliz tilini bilishning muhimligi va ularning xalqaro biznes aloqalarida tutgan o'rni e'tirof etilgan bo'lsa-da, bu masalani yanada chuqurroq o'rganish uchun ko'p ish qilish kerak.

Albatta, til va xalqaro biznes o'rtasidagi munosabatlarga oid tadqiqotlar mavjud, ammo tilning xalqaro biznes munosabatlariga ta'siri bo'yicha bir nechta tadqiqotlar o'tkazilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: Qiymatni oshirish, Aloqa strategiyalari, Lingvistik ta'sir, Manfaatdor tomonlarni jalb qilish, Brend xabarlar, Hikoya qilish, Qiymat taklifi, Ishontiruvchi til, Bozorni idrok etish, Biznes aloqasi.

Asset transformation is the process of creating a new asset (loan) from liabilities (deposits) with different characteristics by converting low-value, easily available and relatively risk-free bank deposits into loans a relatively risky and high-value new asset that I am paid according to a definite plan. An intangible asset is a non-monetary asset that cannot be seen or touched. Tangible assets are physical assets that can be seen, touched, and felt. In accounting, an asset is defined as a current economic resource that has the potential to produce economic benefits. It is recorded on the balance sheet only if it is probable that it will produce economic benefits in the future. Assets can be tangible or intangible[2:24]. An intangible asset is a non-monetary asset that cannot be seen or touched. "Patents or goodwill are good examples," explains Florence Bessette, business consultant, BDC Consulting Services. Tangible assets are physical things. For example, land, buildings, vehicles, furniture and equipment. On the balance sheet, assets are recorded as current and non-current assets long-term assets. Current assets include all assets that the entity expects to realize, sell or consume as part of its normal operating cycle, that it holds for business purposes and that it expects to realize within 12 months of the balance sheet date, as well as available cash. All other assets are recorded as long-term assets. Current assets are generally tangible assets, while long-term assets can be tangible or intangible.[4:41]

Language plays an important role in shaping perceptions and guiding behaviors. The term "stakeholder" is widely used, but little attention is paid to the fact that its use can inadvertently perpetuate colonial narratives and reinforce systemic inequalities. It's all about finding the right words to capture the audience's interest. But that's only part of the story. For the international market, localization—the translation of the website, brand name, and all marketing materials and advertising campaigns into the dominant local language—is the most common brand marketing strategy[3:10]. Localization creates a local personality for a brand while maintaining its international identity. Narrative change must take into account the existing frame of reference held by the target audience and the clarity of how to modify these frames. Transforming assets through innovative technologies, investments and effective management strategies can lead to positive results. In addition, the processes related to the transformation of assets can have not only economic, but also social and environmental effects.[7:17]

This article would explore how language not only serves as a medium for communication but also plays a crucial role in transforming assets, enhancing their value, and fostering stronger relationships with stakeholders.

List of used literature:

1. Ahlu, S. (1997). General English: A consideration of the nature of English as an international medium. *English Today*. 13(1): 17-23.
2. Brealey, RA, Myers, SC, & Allen, F. (2017). *Principles of Corporate Finance*.
3. Brutt-Griffler, J. (2002). *World English: A study of its development*. Clevedon and Buffalo: Multilingual Matters.
4. Drucker, PF (1993). *Post-Capitalist Society*. New York: HarperCollins.
5. Giddens, A. (2000). *Runaway World: How Globalization is reshaping Our Lives*. New York: Routledge.
6. Kachru, B. (1983). *The Other Tongue: English across Cultures*. Oxford: Pergamum.
7. Schilling, MA (2020). *Strategic Management of Technological Innovation* (6th ed.). New York: McGraw-Hill.
8. Smith, A. (1776). *The Wealth of Nations*. London: Methuen & Co.

